

Analysis on Contribution of KCC Scheme in Indian Agricultural Credit

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Abstract: The Indian government is launching several programs for rural and urban areas for agriculture in the country, Kisan credit card scheme is one of them. It is an agriculture credit scheme that was introduced in August 1998 and launched by NABARD & RBI on the recommendation of the Shri R.V. Gupta committee with various objectives for the fulfilment of agricultural credit requirements of the farmers. Short and long-term credit & crop and term loans have been covered in this scheme for agriculture and allied activities. The objectives of the research study are to identify the Agency-Wise & total Contribution of credit under KCC Scheme in Indian Agricultural Credit. Only secondary sources of data and information were used for this research study, which was gathered from publications on the trends and progress of banking in India, RBI, reports of the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, research articles, journals, and websites. The study period has been taken from 2016-17 to 2020-21 & the data was presented in tables and graphs, and MS Excel software was used to analyze it using various statistical methods. It was found that the big contribution of KCC scheme credit in Total agriculture credit of India. In 2017-18, the KCC scheme contribution in total is the highest (57.71%) of all study sessions. when we talked about overall contribution during 2016-17 to 2020-21; the credit flow under KCC Scheme in Indian agriculture credit is 49.64% which is a big contribution. KCC scheme is playing a very big role in the distribution of agriculture credit in India and plays a good role in the development of the agriculture sector.

Key words: KCC Scheme, Agriculture credit, Contribution.

I. INTRODUCTION

India is an agricultural country. Agriculture has been the backbone of India's economy since independence and even before. It remains the largest economic sector in the country and plays an important role in India's overall socio-economic growth & Agriculture sector has the Most Important Sectors of Indian Economy. If any change (positive or negative) in the agricultural sector has multiple impacts on the overall economy. (Sirisha & Malyadri)

Agricultural credit is a technique for providing farmers with both short & long-term financial support from various sources. Agricultural Credit is classified as non institutional and Institutional Credit agencies. The transfer of credit to farmers is handled by many entities. The government of India intends to double farmers' income through various means, hence these organisations are helping farmers financially. PACS, Cooperative Banks, and Land Development Banks offer credit to the poorer section of society at lower interest rates to help them integrate into society and to manage various agricultural operating operations. (Meena, Vikash, & Anubhav)

In 1998-99, the Government of India launched the Kisan credit Card (KCC) Scheme initiative to offer farmers with timely and substantial credit support through the formal banking system in a flexible, hassle-free, and cost-effective manner. This approach has greatly eased the timely availability of credit and has greatly simplified the procedure for obtaining a loan from a bank. The Scheme has been implemented throughout the country by commercial banks, Regional Rural Banks and cooperative banks. It has evolved as a breakthrough credit distribution mechanism for meeting farmers' Agricultural credit needs in a timely and convenient manner.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Bista, Kumar, & Mathur, 2012) have found their own study that the KCC Scheme performs differently in various parts of the nation and among financial institutions. Regarding the KCC Scheme, the Eastern and North-Eastern regions continue to underperform. In Bihar, the flow of loans through KCC has not been very outstanding.

(Godara, Singh, & Singla, 2014) their paper revealed that institutional credit trends to the agricultural sector were higher during the post-reform period than they were during the pre-reform period, and the composition also underwent t significant change during this time. As a result, throughout the post-reform period, indirect lending to the agricultural sector significantly grew. To increase the effectiveness of the credit distribution system in rural areas, the cooperative credit structure needs to be redesigned.

(Dar, 2015) given that the importance of India's agricultural sector is not only in its contribution to GDP, but only in its contribution to employment and livelihoods, their research was of great interest to policy makers, planners, and policy makers to give formal credit to agriculture. Should be a major concern for developers and development economists but because of it's complementarily with other sectors of the economy.

(Chakraborty & Das, 2016) their study period, secondary data was acquired from the Tripura State Level Banker's Committee (SLBC). Tabular analytic methodologies and simple descriptive statistics such as mean, average, percentage, (CAGR), and so on were used. According to the findings, there is a growing tendency in both the volume of KCC advances and the amount of NPA from KCC Advances. Their study found that, the rising trend of NPA in agricultural advances may be stopped by conducting proper assessments to determine the worthiness of the real borrowers and supervising loan after disbursement to monitor the progress of work.

(Chhoidub & Pathania, 2017) analysed their paper "Performance of Kisan Credit Card in Himachal Pradesh: An Empirical Evaluation." The study is empirical in nature, and both primary and secondary data have been used to achieve its objectives. KCC has been used to analyse beneficiaries' impressions of the credit condition using percentage, mean, standard deviation, variance, and standard error of skewness. The majority of respondents were undecided on whether to send in payments for crop insurance premiums under KCCs, the survey indicated. It also found that the respondents' responses were not distributed among them fairly.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objectives: 1. To Overview of the KCC Scheme & Agricultural credit.

2. To Find out the percentage of disbursed credit under KCC Scheme in agricultural credit of India.

3. To Identify the Agency-Wise Contribution in Agriculture credit flow under KCC Scheme.

Hypothesis:

H₀1: The Credit amount disbursed through KCC Scheme in Indian Agriculture credit is less than or equal to 50 % during 2016-17 to 2020-21.

H_a1: The Credit amount disbursed through KCC Scheme in Indian Agriculture credit is more than 50 % during 2016-17 to 2020-21.

H₀2: There is no significant difference in terms of credit flow under KCC Scheme by Co-operative Banks, Regional Rural Banks & Commercial Banks in Indian Agricultural Credit Flow.

H_a2: There is significant difference in terms of credit flow under KCC Scheme by Co-operative Banks, Regional Rural Banks & Commercial Banks in Indian Agricultural Credit Flow.

Research Design:

The study's totally depend on secondary sources of information. The research included the financial years 2016–17 through 2020–21. The information was mostly gathered through the databases of the RBI, NABARD, Banking and Financial Statistics, Economic Survey of the Ministry of Finance, magazines, websites, and the internet, among other sources. Through tables and charts, the examination of the KCC Scheme's role on the Indian credit industry is displayed. Data analysis using various statistical approaches such as Mean, percentage, proportion, and so on is available using MS Excel programme. The study’s has simple analytical approach & descriptive in nature

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 01. Total flow of credit under KCC Scheme in agricultural credit of India.

YEAR	FLOW OF CREDIT TO AGRICULTURE(₹ in CRORE)	CREDIT FLOW UNDER KCC SCHEME(₹ in CRORE)	KCC SCHEME AS PERCENTAGE OF TOTAL AGRICULTURE CREDIT(%)
2016-17	1065755	372730	34.97
2017-18	1162617	670950	57.71
2018-19	1256830	709586.9	56.46
2019-20	1392729	697017.6	50.05
2020-21	1575398	753132.83	47.81
TOTAL	6453329	3203417.33	49.64

Source; Annual report of RBI, Credit delivery and financial Inclusion (rbindocs.rbi.org.in)

Chart 01. Total flow of credit under KCC Scheme in agricultural credit of India.

Above table and chart shows the contribution of KCC scheme credit in Total agriculture credit in India. In 2017-18, KCC scheme contribution in total is highest (57.71%) than the all study session. when we talked about over all contribution during 2016-17 to 2020-21; the credit flow under KCC Scheme in Total agriculture credit is 49.64% that is big contribution.

Table 02. Agency-Wise Contribution in Agriculture credit flow under KCC Scheme.

AGENCY-WISE CREDIT CONTRIBUTION IN AGRICULTURAL CREDIT FLOW						
(Amount in ₹ crore)						
YEAR	FLOW OF CREDIT TO AGRICULTURE			CREDIT FLOW UNDER KCC SCHEME		
	CO-OPERATIVES BANKS	COMMERCIAL BANKS	REGIONAL RURAL BANKS	CO-OPERATIVES BANKS	COMMERCIAL BANKS	REGIONAL RURAL BANKS
2016-17	142758	799781	123216	112200 (78.59%)	158110 (19.77%)	102420 (83.12%)
2017-18	150321	871080	141216	124480 (82.81%)	433110 (49.72%)	113360 (80.27%)
2018-19	152340	954823	149667	127436 (83.65%)	455079.1 (47.66%)	127071.8 (84.90%)
2019-20	157367	1070036	165326	136734.7 (86.89%)	423587.8 (39.59%)	136695.1 (82.68%)
2020-21	190682	1194704	190012	146980.7 (77.081%)	456736.33 (38.23%)	149415.8 (78.63%)
TOTAL	793468	4890424	769437	647831.4 (81.65%)	1926623.23 (39.40%)	628962.7 (81.74%)

Source; Annual report of RBI, Credit delivery and financial Inclusion (rbidocs.rbi.org.in)

Chart 02. Agency-Wise Contribution in Agriculture credit flow under KCC Scheme.

Table & Chart no.02 was shown that the agency-wise flow of credit to the farmers through KCCs in total agriculture credit & these three types of financial institutions are as follows: cooperative banks, regional rural banks & commercial banks. The agency wise share of KCC in the total amount of credit disbursed to agriculture and allied sector during all five financial year from 2016-17 to 2020-21, the Regional Rural banks had given the big contribution of distribution the amount of agriculture credit under KCC Scheme in total credit compare to other two agency like commercial & cooperative banks.

V. FINDINGS

After the analysis chapter we have observed and found that from the table & graph, we can say that:

1. When we talked about over all contribution during 2016-17 to 2020-21; the credit flow under KCC Scheme in Total agriculture credit is 49.64% that is big contribution. **Failing to reject a Null hypothesis**, that means, the Credit amount disbursed through KCC Scheme in Indian Agriculture credit is less than 50 % during 2016-17 to 2020-21.
2. The agency wise share of KCC in the total amount of credit disbursed to agriculture and allied sector during all five financial year from 2016-17 to 2020-21, the RRB (81.74%) had given the big contribution of distribution the amount of agriculture credit under KCC Scheme in total credit compare to other two agency like Cooperative banks (81.65%) & Commercial Banks (39.40%). **Null hypothesis has been rejected** but **Alternate hypo. Was accepted**, that means, there is significant difference in terms of credit flow under KCC Scheme by Co-operative Banks, Regional Rural Banks & Commercial Banks in Indian Agricultural Credit Flow.

VI. CONCLUSION

India is an agricultural country & Agriculture has been the backbone of India's economy. Agriculture credit is giving big contribution in growth & positive changes of agriculture sector in India. KCC scheme is play a very big role in distribution of agriculture credit in India and play a good role in development of agriculture sector, because farmers need money to do farming and the more they get that money through KCC Scheme, the more the farmers will be able to spend more on their farming and production will increase. In the present situation, all these financial loan related work is being possible in large quantity only by KCC Scheme.

VII. REFERENCES

1. Bista, D. R., Kumar, P., & Mathur, V. (2012). Progress and Performance of Kisan Credit Card Scheme Progress and Performance of Kisan Credit Card Scheme. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 25(1), 125-135.
2. Chakraborty, P., & Das, R. C. (2016). Trend of Agricultural credit financed by United bank of India through Kisan Credit Card Scheme in the West Tripura District of Tripura in the Period 2008-09 to 2012-13. *International journal & magazine engineering, technology, management and research*, 3(10), 600-608.
3. Chhoidub, C., & Pathania, S. K. (2017). Performance of Kisan Credit Card in Himachal Pradesh: An Empirical Evaluation. *International Research Journal of Commerce Arts and Science*, 8(11), 317-328.
4. Dar, J. A. (2015). Trend and Growth of Flow of Credit to Agriculture after 1991 in India . *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science*, 20(1), 51-61.
5. Godara, R. L., Singh, P., & Singla, S. (2014). Agriculture Credit in India: An Analytical Study. *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 326-335.
6. Meena, S. S., Vikash, & Anubhav. (n.d.). Source of Agricultural Credit. *Emerging Trends for Commerce and Management*.
7. Sirisha, S., & Malyadri, P. (n.d.). Kisan Credit Card (KCC): a vehicle for financial inclusion. *International Journals of Multidisciplinary Research Academy*, 1(1), 45-53.

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